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Invited Article

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Capt. Achira Telwatta is a distinguished Clinical Psychologist who's serving in the Sri Lankan Army at Army Hospital, Colombo, providing psychological support to service personnel and developing mental health intervention programs. Her expertise in trauma-informed care and psychological well-being has made her a respected voice in Sri Lanka's mental health landscape. She is also a Lecturer and Research Supervisor for the BSc in Psychology and MSc in Clinical and Health Psychology programmes at the University of West London, and a Lecturer for the Diploma in Counselling programme at the University of Sri Jayawardenepura. Capt. Telwatta brings a unique combination of clinical expertise in military mental health and academic experience, which makes her perspective especially valuable for this invited contribution. The editors invited her contribution to offer an expert perspective on *Providing Psychological Support for the Defender of the Nation*.

Providing Psychological Support for the Defender of the Nation

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'Sri Lanka Army' (SLA) is also distinguished as the 'Defender of the Nation' and is known to serve as the nation's backbone whenever the country is faced with challenges (Sri Lanka Army, 2026). Over the past two decades, SLA functioned in multiple roles along with the Sri Lanka Navy and Sri Lanka Air Force in addition to performing the primary role in ensuring national safety and security (Balasuriya, 2025). SLA played a significantly active role in various national crisis situations (ex: Easter Sunday Attack in 2019, COVID 19 Pandemic spread in 2020, Ditwah cyclone in 2025) to offer humanitarian and civil administration support to the Sri Lanka government (Balasuriya, 2025).

SLA, originally named as 'Ceylon Army' was established in 1881, during an era when the country was ruled by the British (Sri Lanka Army, 2026). SLA has roughly 200, 000 personnel currently (Balasuriya, 2024). Army Hospitals (Colombo and Anuradhapura) and Army Base Hospitals (Panagoda, Diyathalawa, Kandy, Kilinochchi, Palali, Minneriya, Mullaitivu) are located around the island to care for the army personnel and their families (Sri Lanka Army, 2026). Currently serving and retired army personnel and their family members are medically supported at these hospitals that are managed by medical professionals employed at SLA.

In addition to typical medical and surgical support provided, a group of about 15 professionals in fields of Psychology and Psychiatry work in the Army Mental Health Unit at Army Hospital - Colombo. The Mental Health Unit (MHU) of SLA comprises Consultant Psychiatrists, Medical Officers, Clinical Psychologists, Psychologists, Counselors and Psychiatric Nurses. This team of individuals are motivated and dedicated to providing psychological, emotional and social support to army personnel identified with psychological, emotional and social issues as in-ward or out-patients.

Experience as the Clinical Psychologist serving in the SLA

Comparing the experience of working in the Army Hospital - Colombo to experience gathered at Government Teaching Hospitals, during the training period, prior to joining with the SLA, it's reasonable to say that the nature of issues handled at SLA are similar to issues that are handled at Government Teaching Hospitals. Disruptions in romantic relationships, friendships, family dynamics or workplace issues as well as a range of clinically diagnosed Psychiatric Disorders such as: Depression, Bipolar Affective Disorder, Schizophrenia, Delusional Disorder, Social Anxiety, Panic Attacks, Substance Misuse Disorders, Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder, Dissociative Disorders, Sexual Dysfunctions, Neuro Cognitive Disorders and Personality Disorders are managed at the MHU in Army.

Disruptions in social networks are commonly handled at Army MHU. These disruptions in social relationships with romantic partners, parents, children, friends and colleagues are largely observed due to obvious reasons such as

poor communication, misunderstandings, excessive commitment towards work, misuse of social media, working away from families for long periods and absence of leave on time. Underlying complex issues such as extra marital affairs, poor or heavy sex drive, substance misuse, delusional disorder (Morbid Jealousy), domestic violence and problematic personality traits (ex: Obsessive-Compulsive, Anti-social, Borderline Personality Disorder) also directly impact maintenance of healthy relationships in families and communities of army personnel.

Generational Trauma is direct or indirect transfer of trauma and various effects of trauma from survivors of trauma (ex: war, abuse, discrimination etc.) to subsequent generations (Gillespie & Graves, 2025). Individuals who have faced various adversities during childhood like parental separation, neglect, alcoholic fathers, low socio-economic state, abuse (physical, emotional or sexual) and exposure to domestic violence display similar abusive and maladaptive behavior as adults highlighting the effects of generational (Gillespie & Graves, 2025). Adverse effects of generational trauma are visible in some families of personnel serving in SLA. Additionally, these individuals show poor coping abilities, low tolerance for injustice, substance misuse habits, poor social skills, poor impulse control and verbal and physical aggression towards self as well as others.

A significant portion of clients treated at army hospital psychiatric clinics are war veterans who have been active in the battlefield during the 30-year civil war. These war heroes are primarily diagnosed with Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), typically comorbid with depressive or anxiety features and substance misuse disorder. PTSD wasn't officially diagnosed as a mental illness among the medical community until publication of DSM III in 1980

(Brewin et al., 2025). However, a syndrome named 'Combat Stress Reaction' was included in previous DMS versions that described psychological and emotional distress experienced by war veterans (Brewin et al., 2025). Commonly observed symptoms in PTSD patients include: re-experiencing (ex: intrusive memories, flashbacks, nightmares), negative alterations in cognitions/ mood (ex: emotional numbness, avoidance) and changes in reactivity (ex: hypervigilance, hyperarousal) (Brewin et al., 2025).

Among the clients treated for PTSD at army hospital psychiatric clinic, there are war heroes who have sustained serious physical injuries during battle as well as some who have not sustained any physical injuries, but psychological trauma, associated with grief and guilt. Veterans who express grief and guilt about their experiences during battle recall their friends, officers who commanded and even opposition members that were killed by them. Brewin et al. (2025) reports that signs of PTSD do not occur immediately after one's exposure to a traumatic event, but it can occur later too. 'Delayed onset of PTSD' is also observed in Sri Lankan war veterans.

A minor portion of psychiatric clients in SLA experience PTSD symptoms following exposure to serious Road traffic accidents, physical and sexual abuse at households and even at camps. Some clients who were harassed at camps experience extreme anxiety symptoms and refuse to report back. Additionally, exposure to natural disasters like Tsunami and Ditwah has also impacted clients to experience PTSD symptoms, especially attached to grief and guilt of survival, while close ones suffered and died.

Hanwella et al. (2012) reports that 'possession' is a state of detachment from an individual's

environment and it is reported in all societies around the world. During the state of procession, one's personal identity is believed to be impacted by invisible external forces such as spirits or devils (Hanwella et al., 2012). During these dissociative episodes individuals typically display signs like screaming, memory impairments, disorientation and involuntary motor movements (Hanwella et al., 2012). Highlighting that SLA is a representation of the Sri Lankan community, a considerable portion of clients who obtain psychological support from the SLA psychiatric unit also express ideas about being possessed by spirits and being victims of traditional charms performed locally. Some of the clients displaying symptoms of dissociations express thoughts about being blessed with powers to cure illness and foresee the future (ex: *Paththini maniyo or Gambara deviyo*). Externalizing personal issues, a considerable number of clients express beliefs about one's misfortune as results of various charms done targeting them or effects of spirits that are cursed on their name.

Drug/s Addiction or Substance Misuse Disorder is a commonly treated condition at psychiatric clinic conducted at Army Hospital. A significant portion of soldiers as well as officers serving in SLA are regular users of alcohol and Nicotine (Cigarettes). Additionally, there are occasional reports of clients who are abusers of heroine, methamphetamine, cannabis and prescribed drugs. Typically, war veterans complain about abuse of alcohol to address sleep disturbances resultant of PTSD. Alcohol abuse habit in war veterans can be identified as a self-medication strategy. A trend observed in military psychiatric clinic these days is an increased number of reports of abusers of Methamphetamine. In rare cases, poly drug abusers are also reported to psychiatric clinic at Army Hospital and

depending on clients' motivation to quit drug misuse habit decisions are taken to discharge active army personnel from the service.

Disorders such as: Anxiety, Depression, Bipolar Affective Disorder and Schizophrenia are also treated at army hospital psychiatric clinic. Clients with a range of anxiety related disorders: social anxiety, panic attacks and illness anxiety are reported. Depressive features are commonly addressed in clients treated at army hospital psychiatric clinic and these symptoms are usually developed secondary to post-partum, family or workplace related issues. Suicidal attempts by overdosing, poisoning and hanging are the types of suicidal attempts are also reported at clinic. Individuals with Bipolar Affective Disorder and Schizophrenia are rarely seen at army hospital psychiatric clinic.

Treatment and Management Strategies used

As mentioned earlier, the MHU at Sri Lanka Army comprised a multidisciplinary team of qualified and trained professionals. However, the unit lacks an adequate number of professionals to deliver the same quality service to all the clients seen at psychiatric clinic. Absence of adequate numbers of qualified and trained members in the psychiatric team sometimes results in team members feeling overworked and even failing to cater to the needs of the organization as expected.

Despite the challenge of handling a large number of clients at the psychiatric clinic, clients are offered a variety of treatments and services depending on the issue/s. Symptoms are typically managed pharmacologically while emotional and psychological support is offered with counseling and other talk therapies. Despite effectiveness, the benefits of advanced therapeutic techniques from Cognitive Behavior Therapy, the use of advanced techniques are

often challenging due to intellectual capacities of typical clients seen. MHU is also equipped to offer Electro Convulsive Therapy (ECT) and it's typically used with severe depression, severe PTSD and sever psychosis. Further, it's important to note that ECT is used as the last option when medication fail to improve symptoms in clients.

Relationship issues, marital issues and workplace issues are also managed through contacting necessary parties (ex: girlfriend, parents, spouse, in laws, Commanding Officers etc.). Additionally, local authorities such as: Probation services are also contacted and informed to offer support and supervision as required. Many clients in SLA fail to attend regular counseling sessions at Army hospital due to various practical issues such as: work commitments, location of camps, financial difficulties and family/ social commitments. Further, some clients report poor drugs compliance claiming inability to perform normal duties, especially night duties due to drowsiness from drugs. Failure to comply with recommended counseling/ therapy session and poor drug compliance stands in the way of obtaining expected improvements in clients' symptoms, relationships and overall wellbeing.

War heroes who have sustained serious physical injuries during battle, were prematurely discharged from the army considering the seriousness of the injury and limitations in offering a productive service to the organization. These war veterans are offered financial compensations or disability pension as a tribute to their sacrifice during the battle. Further to veterans who have sustained visible physical injuries, measures are taken to approve compensations and disability pension to those sustained significant psychological damage and functional impairment due to PTSD symptoms.

War veterans who have sustained serious physical injuries were treated, rehabilitated and cared at residential institutes built in Ragama, Anuradhapura, Kurunegala, Kamburupitiya and Attidiya areas namely Rana Wiru Swana, Abhimansal and Mihindu Seth Madura. In addition to veterans who sustained physical injuries, those affected psychologically as well as those without proper family support are also cared for at these institutes.

Many families seen at the army hospital psychiatric clinic are dysfunctional as depicted earlier, due to various reasons ranging from unhealthy habits to psychiatric illnesses or personality issues. Reuniting and harmonizing the broken family bonds to create a safe and warm environment for children has been a serious challenge. Sometimes the assistance of extended family is also obtained when both parents are under psychiatric care. In highly dysfunctional families, the dysfunctional parents are advised to live separately and perform responsibilities to support the children financially and materialistically as required.

Reflection on the Experiences and Challenges Faced

Being a part of Sri Lanka Army's psychiatric unit is a highly rewarding experience that allows working with and working for a special community, whose service to the nation is unmatched. As noted earlier, the nature of issues seen and treated at the unit are similar to issues handled at general hospitals, but the management of issues is different at SLA. Sometimes, uncommon decisions are taken considering the effectiveness and productivity of clients towards the organization that leads in clients losing their employment.

The military is a highly structured organization, and it functions and relies heavily on ranks and

power. Practice of traditional client-centered approaches is neither practical nor effective in the military setting due to the power and respect clients hold towards the professionals and ranks within the organization. Further, the presence of ranks and hierarchy has facilitated clients' adherence with medical advice and drug compliance. Collaboration with respective camps is also beneficial in managing clients' symptoms and supervising productivity.

Managing issues in dysfunctional families/marriages is immensely challenging, especially when neither of the parties agrees to compromise. Further, clients who are unwilling to accept their difficult habits and personality traits as well as the impact on close ones make the time and effort go wasted. Even though morbid jealousy and heavy irritability is a primary cause of family disruptions, convincing clients on drug compliance is a nearly impossible task despite multiple sessions of psychoeducation.

Sri Lankan community places an importance on effects of spirits and demons on humans even today. Attempting to address underlying chronic stressors with proper psychoeducation and empowering clients with healthy coping mechanisms aren't effective with clients who hold strong beliefs about effects of traditional charms. Dissociations or dissociative episodes are successfully intervened when clients' beliefs are strategically challenged while introducing problem solving techniques.

A significant portion of clients treated for PTSD can recall harrowing memories at the battlefield. Some war heroes recall incidents vividly with specific dates, names of people and places where attacks happened. While some recall battle memories with grief and guilt, some recall their heroic acts with extreme pride and honor.

Importantly, some are proud to claim their participation and contribution in the battle. Deep discussions with clients who have been active widen the understanding of the brutality of battle.

Being a member of MHU at SLA is an unmatched and fulfilling experience that wouldn't be traded under any circumstance. Moreover, recognition within the team and visible improvements in clients serves as a motivation to provide a better quality service to the army personnel and their families.

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